

Tasks analysis for handwashing

Scoring scale				
Not complete (with any form of prompting)	Physical prompting (continuous)	Physical prompting (Intermittent)	Verbal, Visual or gesture prompting	Complete independently
0	1	2	3	4

No.	Session No. (.....).		Date:			
	Phase:		Evaluator:			
Student name:		Total score:				
	Steps	Not complete	Physical prompting (continuous)	Physical prompting (Intermittent)	Verbal, Visual or gesture prompting	Complete independently
1	Stand front of the sink	0	1	2	3	4
2	Open the water tap	0	1	2	3	4
3	Put hands in the water	0	1	2	3	4
4	Get the soap	0	1	2	3	4
5	Rub hands palm to palm in a circular motion	0	1	2	3	4
6	Scrub between fingers (back and forth)	0	1	2	3	4
7	Clean both thumbs	0	1	2	3	4
8	Clean the back of your hands	0	1	2	3	4
9	Rub your fingers on the palms	0	1	2	3	4
10	Clean the wrist of both hands	0	1	2	3	4
11	Rise hands	0	1	2	3	4
12	Turn off water	0	1	2	3	4
13	Pick the towel	0	1	2	3	4
14	Dry hands	0	1	2	3	4
15	Place the towel in the place	0	1	2	3	4
Total score						
Percentage: $\text{Sum}/60 \times 100$						